

Effectiveness Of External Monitoring System In Government Schools Of Punjab

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 07, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 08, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Monitoring, Punjab, School Council, Educational Facilities, Administration</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5558018</p>	<p>Purpose: <i>The present study was conducted to find out the effectiveness of External Monitoring Systems in government schools of Punjab-Pakistan.</i></p> <p>Methodology: <i>The study was descriptive and survey method was used to collect the data. Multi stage sampling technique was used. Out of 36, 16 DEO and 16 DMO, 320 head teachers, 640 teachers and 320 Monitoring and Evaluation Assistant were randomly selected from each selected. Data were collected through self structured questionnaires from five stakeholders. Collected data were analyzed by using Means, Standard Deviations, Mean of Mean, ANOVA and Post-hocks test as statistical instruments.</i></p> <p>Results: <i>It was concluded that External Monitoring was effective in three variables (monitoring of educational facilities, school councils and general administration of principals).</i></p> <p>Recommendations: <i>It was recommended that for more fruitful External Monitoring, the MEAs may be appointed fresh graduate from education field so that they may be able to deliver model lesson and motivate the teachers during their visits.</i></p>

Introduction

No doubt, monitoring is essential component of management. Organization can never achieve its objectives without proper monitoring. That is why, there is a systematic and effective monitoring system in all organizations of the developed countries of the world. Monitoring is an essential component of management for effective implementation of any programme. It is an essential ingredient of proper evaluation (Mehmood, et. al. 2021). According to Mahmood (2016) monitoring is an aspect of both accountability and development.

Monitoring is a continuous process of collecting information, providing check and balance and presenting factual position of assigned work (Shah, 2009). It is a continuous process of gathering relevant information (Shami, 2013). It is observation of the activities and their contexts, inputs, process and results. It also involves communication of results to appropriate level of management and storage of information for future evaluation (Shami, 2009).

Educational monitoring involves steps of formulating objectives, setting tools, and attaining aims of education. It observes educational programme vigilantly to ensure whether it is in accordance to set schedule or not. Like other departments, all countries of the world have their own monitoring systems of education. Effective monitoring is an important part of management of officers for ensuring quality education (Shah, 2009).

Government of Punjab (2001) had reformed in education sector under Punjab Education Sector Reforms Program (PESRP) in 2000. Quality of education is among three pillars of PESRP. In order to implement and look after the third pillar of PESRP, the provincial government had introduced an external monitoring system in 2001 under the act of devolution of power. The department namely Program Monitoring and Implementation Unit (PMIU) was established to increase access to education, to improve governance, to improve quality of education and to support devolution by allocating more financial resources at provincial and district level in the province of Punjab.

In this monitoring system, the separate department namely Program Monitoring and Implementation Unit (PMIU) monitors programme and projects of the government of Punjab. Thirty-five District Monitoring Officers (DMOs) in all 35 districts of the province were appointed for the said purpose (later on one new district was formed hence now there are 36 DMOs in 36 districts). These DMOs had been appointed directly by the Chief Minister Secretariat after recommendation of services and general administration department of the provincial government and they were appointed from District Management Group.

To monitor educational programme, a sub department of PMIU was established which is called Monitoring Cell. Retired Junior Commissioned Officers of army (JCOs) were appointed to visit schools and to collect data. These new appointed field workers were given the designation of Monitoring and Evaluation Assistants (MEAs). They prepare monthly report and sent it to District Monitoring Officer. District Monitoring Officers issue monthly reports and send its copies to corresponding District Coordinating Officer (DCO) and Chief Minister of Punjab.

It is the duty of DCO to give instruction to concerned education officers for taking action according to report of DMO. DCO also reports to Chief Minister about reports and his/her action. Both the departments are working under the same head namely DCO at district level. Monitoring system captures data from public educational system that is regularly validated by the third party (Government of Punjab, 2001). The statistic showed that the province of Punjab had improved herself in education sector through PESRP with the help of monitoring stakeholders (EDO-E, DEO, DMO, MEA and Head Teacher). Enrolment at primary and secondary level has increased under PESRP (Government of Punjab, 2007).

There are many factors responsible for these gains like media campaign, government effort and commitment, internal and external monitoring and devolution of power. All factors depend on monitoring because facts and figures provided by monitoring system, help educational managers to take corrective measures. To find out the effectiveness of external monitoring system, the researcher decided to study on monitoring systems of Punjab. Another reason which inspired the researcher to conduct study on this topic was the gap of research in this field. No work seems to have been done on the present topic or relevant to this topic. This research work was carried out to fill this gap.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

To assess the effectiveness of External Monitoring System in monitoring educational and hygienic facilities, performance of school councils, and administration of government school in Punjab

To compare the views of stakeholders and respondents about the effectiveness of External Monitoring System in Punjab Education Department.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Following were the research questions of the study;

1. To what extent the External Monitoring System in Punjab school department is effective in ensuring educational and hygienic facilities in government schools of Punjab?
2. To what extent the External Monitoring System in Punjab school department is effective in monitoring school councils in government schools of Punjab?
3. To what extent the External Monitoring System in Punjab school department is effective in monitoring general administration of schools principals in government schools of Punjab?
4. What is difference among the opinions of stakeholders about the performance of External Monitoring System in Punjab Education Department in term of educational and hygienic facilities, school councils, and general administration of school principals?

METHODOLOGY

This study was descriptive by purpose and survey by method. Following procedure was adopted to conduct the research.

POPULATION

The population of the study consisted of five stakeholders. The information about the population size was taken from the official website of the government of Punjab. The detail of the five stakeholders is as follows:

1. **District Monitoring Officer (DMO):** DMO is overall head of External Monitoring System at district level. So the entire 36 DMOs working in Punjab were included in population.
2. **District Education Officers-Secondary (DEOs-Sec):** DEO-Sec is administrator of secondary schools at district level. Hence all 36 DEOs-Secondary were included in population.
3. **Head of Secondary School:** Head teacher is immediate boss at school level. Therefore, all 4,498 head-teachers performing their duties in 4498 government secondary schools in Punjab were included in population.
4. **Secondary School Teacher:** Secondary school teachers know the true performance of External Monitoring at secondary school level as he/she is witness of the monitoring system. So all 25145 secondary school teachers were included in population.
5. **Monitoring and Evaluation Assistant (MEA):** MEA is a field worker of External Monitoring System. Hence all 1,078 MEAs working in Punjab were included in the population.

In this way the total population size was 30,792 (36 DMOs, 36 DEOs_ sec., 4498 head teachers, 25145 secondary school teachers and 1078 MEAs) individuals of the Punjab education department.

SAMPLE

According to Easton and McColl (2015) multistage sampling technique is suitable for studying the big and heterogeneous population. Due to different category of respondents multistage sampling technique was applied and total 1312 (16 DMOs, 16 DEOs, 320 MEAs, 320 Head Teachers, and 640 Teachers) respondents were selected from the whole Punjab.

Sampling Procedure: Multistage Sampling

1st Stage: Randomly selection of 16 districts

2nd Stage: Universally selection of all 16 DMOs and 16 DEOs

3rd Stage: Randomly selection of 320 MEAs (20 from each sample district)

4th Stage: Randomly selection of 320 Head teachers (20 from each sample district)

5th Stage: Randomly selection of 640 teachers (40 from each sample district)

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

A self-developed questionnaire having 10 statements, were developed to assess the effectiveness of External Monitoring on Likert scale. Five statements were about the monitoring of educational and hygienic facilities, two were about monitoring of school councils and three were about the general administration of schools principals.

Validity of Instrument

The validity of the questionnaire was adjudged by the panel of experts consisting of 10 educationists. It was found valid to achieve the objectives of the research.

Pilot Testing

For pilot testing, 5 DMOs, 5 DEOs, 40 MEAs, 80 head-teachers and 160 teachers were selected from 4 districts of the Punjab which were not included in sample. The data was collected personally so the response rate for pilot testing was 93 %.

Reliability

To find the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach's coefficient Alpha formula was applied by using SPSS Version 21 to estimate the internal consistency of items on collected data for pilot testing. The obtained Cronbach's alpha was 0.83. Hence, no any item was dropped from the questionnaire.

DATA COLLECTION

The questionnaires were sent and received through Pakistan postal mail. Fifty four (54 %) percent responses were received in first attempt. Reminders were sent to respondents and 13 % more responses were received. To take more response, again reminders were sent to respondents and 5 % more responses were received. Once more, it was tried to get response but it was useless. It took one year and 6 months of researcher, so the data were analyzed through 76 % response rate.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The collected data were analyzed by using, mean, Standard Deviation, ANOVA and Post Hoc Tukey test as statistical tool. Arithmetic mean, SD and average of means were used to assess the effectiveness of External Monitoring. To find the difference among means of opinions of different stakeholders ANOVA and Post-Hoc Tukey test were applied.

ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF DATA

Table 1: Effectiveness of External Monitoring System

Serial No.	Variables	N	Group Mean	Std. Deviation	Means of mean
1	Facilities	990	17.3752	4.57260	3.47
2	School Councils	990	6.6539	2.00466	3.32
3	General Administration	990	14.6162	3.10614	3.65

Categorization of mean

1. 1.00 to 2.00 below average
2. 2.00 to 3.00 moderate
3. 3.00 to 5.00 above average

Table 1 is measurement of views of stakeholders about the performance of External Monitoring System in respect of different variables. The table shows that there is difference among the mean scores of different variables but the means scores of each variable is greater than 3. It means score of all three variables falls in the category of above average while score of two variables falls in moderate range. It indicates that External Monitoring is effective in term of increasing the students attendance and enrolment, controlling the teacher absenteeism, collection and utilization of funds and overall administration in secondary schools of Punjab. But it is comparatively less effective in term of provision of facilities to schools, active involvement of school councils in secondary schools of Punjab. The same were the findings of the research conducted by Muneer, M.K.; Naseem, B; Anisa, K. &Shazia, N. (2011).

Table 2 Comparison of views of stakeholders about the performance of External Monitoring System in term of facilities

Facilities	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	267.654	4	66.914	3.246	0.113
Within Groups	13197.549	985	20.621		
Total	13465.203	989			

The above table 2 shows that $F(4, 985) = 3.246$ and the value of $p = 0.113$ is greater than 0.05. It reveals that there is no significant difference among the views of all stakeholders about performance of External Monitoring System in respect of monitoring of educational facilities. It means that respondents with different designations have almost same views about the performance of External Monitoring System in respect of monitoring of educational facilities in secondary schools of Punjab Education Department.

Table 3 Comparison of views of stakeholders about the performance of External Monitoring System in term of monitoring of school councils

School Council	Sum of Squares	d.f	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	109.685	4	27.421	7.026	.0001
Within Groups	3137.405	986	3.902		
Total	3247.090	990			

The above table 3 shows that $F(4, 985) = 7.026$ and the value of $p = 0.0001$ is less than 0.05. It reveals that there is significant difference among the views of all stakeholders about performance of External Monitoring System in respect of school councils. It means that respondents with different designations have different views about the performance of External Monitoring System in respect of monitoring of school councils in secondary schools of Punjab Education Department.

Table 4 Multiple comparison of views of stakeholders about the performance of External Monitoring System in term of monitoring of school councils

(I) Designation	(J) Designation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
1 DMO	2 DEO	1.49624	.69578	.200
	3 Head Teacher	1.36998	.54832	.092
	4 Teacher	1.88571*	.53536	.004*
	5 MEA	1.11096	.56269	.279
2 DEO	3 Head Teacher	-.12626	.47676	.999
	4 Teacher	.38947	.46181	.917
	5 MEA	-.38528	.49322	.936
3 Head Teacher	4 Teacher	.51573*	.17264	.024*
	5 MEA	-.25903	.24456	.827
4 Teacher	5 MEA	-.77476*	.21394	.003*

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The table 4 indicates that there is significant difference among the opinion of teachers, head teachers, District Monitoring Officers (DMOs) and Monitoring and Evaluation Assistant (MEAs). The table shows that teachers have different views about performance of External Monitoring in term of monitoring of school councils from other stakeholders. The mean differences show that the opinion of DMOs are more in favour of External Monitoring in term of monitoring of school councils than the opinions of other stakeholders. The table also shows that there is no significant difference among the opinions of other stakeholders in this regard. The possible reason might be the affiliation of DMOs with External Monitoring as a stakeholder therefore their opinions support the External Monitoring.

Table 5 Comparison of views of stakeholders about the performance of External Monitoring System in term of general administration

Administration	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	311.333	4	77.833	8.361	.0001
Within Groups	7522.933	808	9.311		
Total	7834.266	812			

The above table 5 shows that $F(4, 808) = 8.361$ and the value of $p = 0.0001$ is less than 0.05. It reveals that there is significant difference among the views of all stakeholders about performance of External Monitoring System in respect of general administration. It means that respondents with different designation have different views about the performance of External Monitoring System in respect of monitoring of general administration.

Table 6 Multiple comparison of views of stakeholders about the performance of External Monitoring System in term of general administration

(I) Designation	(J) Designation	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
1 DMO	2 DEO	1.79698	1.07473	.451
	3 Head Teacher	.82418	.84628	.866
	4 Teacher	2.07908	.82696	.087
	5 MEA	2.52565*	.86916	.031*
2 DEO	3 Head Teacher	-.97282	.73565	.677
	4 Teacher	.28207	.71332	.996
	5 MEA	.72866	.76185	.873
3 Head Teacher	4 Teacher	1.25491*	.26452	.000*
	5 MEA	1.70147*	.37624	.000*
4 Teacher	5 MEA	.44657	.33046	.658

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

The table 5 indicates that there is significant difference among the opinion of DMOs, head teachers, teachers and monitoring and evaluation assistants (MEAs). The mean differences show that the opinions of DMOs are more in favour of External Monitoring in term of monitoring of general administration than the opinions of others stakeholders. It might be due to personal affiliation of DMOs with External Monitoring as DMOs are stakeholder of External Monitoring therefore their opinions are in favour of External Monitoring.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It was found that overall performance of External Monitoring is above average. External Monitoring is found effective in term of provision of facilities to schools, active involvement of school councils and overall administration in secondary schools of Punjab. These findings are in the line with the results of research paper conducted by Muneer, Naseem, Aneesa and Shazia (2011).

It is found that the opinions of DMOs are comparatively more in favour of performance of External Monitoring, in term of school councils than the opinions of other stakeholders. It might be due to personal biasness of the stakeholder as DMO and MEA are stakeholders of External Monitoring System. And it is natural that average persons like their own system or department. Therefore opinions of DMOs and MEAs are found in favour of their own system.

There is no significant difference among the views of all stakeholders about performance of External Monitoring System in respect of monitoring of educational facilities. On the other hand it is found that the opinions of DMOs are more in favour of External Monitoring in term of monitoring of general administration than the opinions of other stakeholders. It was also found by Muneer, Naseem, Aneesa and Shazia (2011). The findings of Mahmood, Anwar and Khan (2012) also support this point of view. The findings of Mehmood et.al (2021) also support these results.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Education service academy may be established where managerial training may be given to officer of education department. There may be six month training for new appointed officers of education department and one month training in every year so that education officers may be equipped with update knowledge and skills of educational management and leadership of the world. Training for monitoring may be emphasized along with other management functions like planning, organizing, controlling, budgeting, and directing etc.
2. A separate wing for monitoring may be established consisting on fresh appointment or retired educational officers. DEO monitoring may be appointed in each district of Punjab assisted with field staff to visit schools and maintain record. As the present External Monitoring in Punjab is working by the name of Chief Minister Monitoring Force. They have many other departments to monitor like hospitals besides this they are irrelevant person and not much effective in education department. As they are not able to monitor the scheme of study, lesson planning and classroom management etc. Hence they cannot perform well except paper work.
3. School plant management, health and hygienic facilities, educational facilities, library, laboratories, play ground, clean and sufficient water, boundary wall, classrooms, offices, school record, funds record, furniture, students attendance, enrolment, dropout, retention, teachers attendance and result of school must be monitored.
4. Provision of facilities to schools may be granted on the reports of monitoring officers and collection and consumption of funds may be monitored by monitoring team.
5. This research was delimited to secondary schools of Punjab only. Other researches on new dimension/such topics may be conducted at elementary, and collage level in Punjab as well as other provinces, AJK and Islamabad Capital Territory. Some other indicators of successful monitoring like schools results, learning ability, and skills like reading and writing may also be studied. Effectiveness of 3rd party monitoring may also be studied. In the same way, effects of stipend program, free distribution of books, and emergency campaign for increasing enrolment may also be studied.

Acknowledgements or Notes

It is submitted that this article is our original research work is not published anywhere else. If ant thing is found against the law, we will be responsible.

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